

Handling Unbalanced Data on Binary Image Segmentation Modeling Using Kolmogorov Forward Theory and External Force

Tiana Razefania Ramahefy

Engineering Science, Université de Vakinankaratra, Madagascar

Rivo Mahandrisoa Randriamaroson

SE-I-MSDE, ED-STII, Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar

ABSTRACT:

A binary image with imbalanced data refers to an image in which pixel classes are not equally represented. In other words, one class is much more present than the other. In the case of the binary image, the concentration of black pixels on a white background is not balanced. The image could have a large majority of white pixels with some sporadically scattered black areas or conversely a small number of white pixels could be surrounded by a large area of black pixels. In imbalanced images, where one class is significantly overrepresented, some segmentation algorithms may have difficulty identifying objects or boundaries. This can lead to biased results. If the segmentation is performed using a supervised learning model, a severe imbalance can lead to biased learning where the model favors the majority class. This can give unsatisfactory results because the model does not properly learn to segment the pixels of the minority class. The aim of this article is to design a method to use the cost function based on the resampling method to balance the image data, thereby exposing the two black and white classes to a more representative proportion, which can improve the detection and segmentation of target objects via the Kolmogorov forward equation which is derived from the Fokker-Planck equation.

Keywords: intelligence artificial, unbalanced data, Kolmogorov equation, cost function, deep learning.

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INTRODUCTION

Processing binary images with imbalanced data is a recurring problem in computer vision applications, especially when one of the classes is significantly underrepresented compared to the other [1]. This imbalance can pose several challenges in classification tasks, as machine learning models can be biased towards the majority class, leading to poor performance on the minority class [2]. Image segmentation using the Kolmogorov forward equation generally refers to mathematical approaches based on graph theory and variational models, particularly in the context of maximum flow and minimum cut image segmentation methods. To model the segmentation boundaries of binary images with imbalanced data via the Kolmogorov forward equation, we need to integrate the concepts of diffusion and regularization into the segmentation process.

METHODOLOGY

The Kolmogorov forward equation, which is closely linked with Fokker-Planck equation, focuses on the time evolution of the probability density of a stochastic system. In the context of image

segmentation, this approach can be adapted to model probabilistic transitions between image regions and the evolution of contours in a regularized manner. The goal of the algorithm is to smooth the boundaries between these two classes while preserving essential features, such as the contours of the object or the image itself.

Binarization of the Image

Binarizing an image consists of converting a grayscale image into a binary image, where each pixel takes only two possible values: 0 for black and 1 for white. Let $I(x, y)$ be the intensity of a pixel at position (x, y) in a grayscale image. The intensity is a real value between 0 and 255 for an 8-bit grayscale image. The principle of binarization is as follows:

$$B(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } I(x, y) > T \\ 0, & \text{if } I(x, y) < T \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where: $B(x, y)$ – value of the binary pixel (1 or 0), $I(x, y)$ – intensity value of the initial pixel in grayscale, T – given threshold (fixed or adaptive).

Identification of Unbalanced Classes

In a given image the majority class is the background of the image, represented by high intensities. The background covers a larger area in general. The minority class is often the lower intensities. They occupy a much smaller portion of the image. The imbalances are evident in this case because the image itself represents a significantly smaller fraction of the pixels, which can complicate the correct segmentation of objects.

Segmentation modeling

a) Mathematical modeling of the problem

Fokker-Planck equation could be used to model the probability density $p(x, y, t)$ of image boundaries or contours as a function of spatial coordinates (x, y) and time t , the function $p(x, y, t)$ could represent the probability that pixel (x, y) is part of a boundary at time t . The Kolmogorov forward equation, which is closely linked to the Fokker-Planck equation, focuses on the time evolution of the probability density of a stochastic system from an initial condition looking into the future. In the context of image segmentation, this approach could be adapted to model probabilistic transitions between image regions and the evolution of contours in a regularized manner. The Kolmogorov forward equation is then [3]:

$$\frac{\partial p(x, y, t)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (A(x, y, t) p(x, y, t)) + \nabla^2 (B(x, y, t) p(x, y, t)) \quad (2)$$

Where:

$p(x, y, t)$ – probability that the point (x, y) is on the boundary of the object in the image at time t . It can be used to define a segmentation function that evolves over time and tends to converge to a stable solution, where each pixel in the image is assigned to a region or class,

$A(x, y, t)$ – derivative term that can represent a force that pushes the boundaries in a certain direction (for example, to attract contours to regions of high gradient in the image),

$B(x, y, t)$ – diffusion term, which controls how the probability spreads across the image. This term acts as a smoothing, allowing small irregularities or noise to be removed from the boundary. This helps to obtain more regular and consistent contours;

$\nabla \cdot (\dots)$ – divergence (differential operator), which indicates how the probability density moves across the image;

∇^2 (...) – Laplacian, which models the diffusion of the probability density across the image.

The Kolmogorov forward equation can thus be compared to active contour (snake)-based segmentation methods, where a curve evolves in the image to detect the contours of an object. In this case, the drift $A(x, y, t)$ could be interpreted as an external force that attracts the boundaries towards areas of high gradient, while the diffusion $B(x, y, t)$ plays a smoothing role to regularize these boundaries.

b) Choice of data representation

i. Reducing image resolution

To make manual calculations easier, we reduced the image resolution. We converted the image to a grid of dimension (4,4) or 4x4 pixels in grayscale. The simplified grid has grayscale values expressed from 0 to 255, where 0 is black and 255 is white.

ii. Boundary detection

To detect the boundaries between the image itself and the background, we use gradients. The intensity gradient is calculated by taking the difference between neighboring pixels. • The gradient is used to detect the contours of objects. Here is the method to calculate horizontal and vertical gradients:

The horizontal gradient ∇_x represents the difference between a pixel and its neighbor on the right.

$$\nabla_x I(x, y) = I(x + 1, y) - I(x, y) \quad (3)$$

The vertical gradient ∇_y represents the difference between a pixel and its bottom neighbor.

$$\nabla_y I(x, y) = I(x, y + 1) - I(x, y) \quad (4)$$

The total gradient at each point can be calculated as the norm of the horizontal and vertical gradients

$$\|\nabla I(x, y)\| = \sqrt{(\nabla_x I(x, y))^2 + (\nabla_y I(x, y))^2} \quad (5)$$

Segmentation

We currently have a matrix of values representing the total gradient of each pixel. Pixels with a high gradient (close to the image itself) will have a high value, while those in more uniform regions (background) will have a lower value. We will apply a threshold to separate objects from the background. For example, all pixels with a gradient norm greater than a certain value will be classified as belonging to the object (or the image itself) and conversely the background image has a gradient norm lower than this reference value.

Calculation of Diffusion

Diffusion (Laplacian) smooths contours between areas with intensity differences. The Laplacian $\nabla^2 u(x, y)$ is a discrete approximation of the second derivative and we apply it to each pixel $u(x, y)$. It calculates the difference between the intensity of a pixel and the average of its immediate neighbors. The Laplacian measures the local curvature of the pixel intensity, which helps smooth edges. For each pixel, the Laplacian is calculated by subtracting its value from that of its neighbors [4].

$$\nabla^2 u(x, y) = u(x + 1, y) + u(x - 1, y) + u(x, y + 1) + u(x, y - 1) - 4u(x, y) \quad (6)$$

Handling Unbalanced Data by Weighting the External Force

Numerical application of the intensity-based external force in a Kolmogorov forward equation for image segmentation involves integrating a force that guides the segmentation towards regions where the pixel intensity differs from the background. This external force plays a key role in directing the segmentation towards the objects of interest (here, butterflies) in the image, while influencing the edges.

The external force $f(x, y)$ is often derived from the difference between the pixel intensity and a reference intensity (e.g., the average background intensity). In our case, we will use the PNG image converted to grayscale, where each pixel has an intensity between 0 (black) and 255 (white).

The idea is to define a force that:

- Pushes the edges away from the segmentation if they are close to the background intensity.
- Attracts the edges if they are close to the intensity of the objects (butterflies).

External force can be defined as:

$$f(x, y) = -(I(x, y) - I_{fond_moyen}) \quad (7)$$

Where: $I(x, y)$ – intensity at pixel (x, y) , I_{fond_moyen} – average intensity of the background image calculated from the areas assumed to belong to the background.

The negative sign in this equation ensures that pixels with a lower intensity than the background (darker objects i.e. the image itself) will be attracted to the objects, while lighter pixels will be repelled.

Regularization of Segmentation

We use smoothing by applying a local average on the gradient values to eliminate small noise variations. This regularization of the segmentation is done in two stages such as updating the intensities and repeating the iterations.

a) Updating pixel intensities

Updating the intensity of a pixel is done by combining:

- The diffusion term (Laplacian), which smooths the transition between neighboring pixels.
- The weighted external force, which adjusts the intensity according to the minority or majority class.

$u(x, y)$ is updated by [5]:

$$u(x, y) = u(x, y) + D\nabla^2 u(x, y) + f(x, y) \quad (8)$$

Where D – given constant which is the diffusion coefficient.

The pixels of minority objects see their intensity increase more quickly to compensate for the imbalance with the background pixels.

b) Progressive regularization by repetition of iterations

This process is repeated for each pixel in the matrix, which allows the image to be regularized by taking into account both the diffusion and the external force weighted for the objects and the background.

The process is repeated over several iterations to stabilize the intensities. At each step:

- The background pixels stabilize, because their intensity is close to the average intensity of the background, and the external force is weak.

- The object pixels see their intensities gradually increase thanks to the weighting of the external force, which helps to preserve their edges and prevent them from disappearing.

RESULTS

In this article we take the image of butterflies [6] in Figure 1 as a source of PNG image still non-binary. Then we use python and its packages like numpy, matplotlib and networks to help to transform it to grayscale and to get the values in some used tables. Using this application may help us to get the result images and mostly more focus on our methodology.

Figure 1. Butterfly Source Image in PNG

A simplified version of the image has been used, i.e. a small subset of the image, as a 4x4 pixel matrix. We will simulate the following steps for an area with intensity differences on the butterfly object vs its background. The following Table1 is a 4x4 matrix representing the image. Each value constitutes the intensity of a pixel ranging from 0 to 255 (0 = black, 255 = white).

Table 1. Reduced Matrix Representing the Image

Pixel $u(x, y)$	1	2	3	4
1	200	200	210	210
2	200	200	210	210
3	50	50	60	60
4	50	50	60	60

We can deduce that 200-210 corresponds to the background with a light color and what belongs to 50-60 corresponds to the object more precisely to the butterfly with a dark color.

Calculation of the Average Background Intensity

The average background intensity (pixels around the butterflies) can be estimated by taking the average of the background values.

$$I_{fond_moyen} = \frac{200 + 200 + 200 + 200 + 210 + 210 + 210 + 210}{8} = 205$$

Calculation of the External Force

As a reminder, the external force $f(x, y)$ at each pixel is given by equation (7)

Thus, for $f(1, 1) = - (200 - 205) = - 5$ and so on for the other pixel cells that can be summarized on the Table 2 below.

Table 2. Result of External Force at Each Pixel

$f(x, y)$	1	2	3	4
1	5	5	-5	-5
2	5	5	-5	-5
3	155	155	145	145
4	155	155	145	145

These values indicate the direction of the force:

Positive values mean that the pixels are darker than the background, so the force pulls those pixels inward (toward the object, butterfly).

Negative values mean that the pixels are brighter than the background, so the force pulls those pixels outward (toward the background).

Diffusion Regularization

For $u(2, 2)$, we use equation (6) of the Laplacian calculation, and we will have:

- $u(2, 2) = 200$
- The neighbors of $u(2, 2)$ are:
 $u(1, 2) = 200, u(3, 2) = 50, u(2, 1) = 200, u(2, 3) = 210$

So, the Laplacian of $u(2, 2)$ is then

$$\nabla^2 u(2, 2) = \frac{1}{4} [200 + 50 + 200 + 210 - 4 * 200]$$

$$\nabla^2 u(2, 2) = \frac{1}{4} [660 - 800] = \frac{1}{4} (-140) = - 35$$

The result is a negative value, which means that this pixel will be attracted to the average intensity of its neighbors (smoothing).

By opting for the same calculation principle, we obtain the result on the table3:

Table 3. Result of Laplacian calculation

$\nabla^2 u(x, y)$	1	2	3	4
1	-20	-20	-30	-30
2	-20	-35	-30	-30
3	75	75	65	65
4	75	75	65	65

Segmentation Update

Let: Diffusion coefficient – $D=0,25$; average intensity of the background image = 205

Applying equation (8) we obtain a new value of the intensity of each pixel:

For le pixel (1,1):

The initial intensity: $u(1, 1) = 200$

The Laplacian $\nabla^2 u(1, 1)$ using the immediate neighbors is: $\nabla^2 u(1, 1) = - 20$

The external force for this point is: $f(1, 1) = 5$

The new intensity is thus:

$$u(1,1) = 200 + 0,25 * (-20) + 5 = 200 - 5 + 5 = 200$$

For le pixel (2, 2):

The initial intensity: $u(2,2) = 200$

The Laplacian $\nabla^2 u(1,1)$ using the immediate neighbors is: $\nabla^2 u(1,1) = -35$

The external force for this point is: $f(2,2) = 5$

The new intensity is thus:

$$u(1,1) = 200 + 0,25 * (-35) + 5 = 186,5$$

and so on for all the pixel from (1, 1) to (4, 4).

The following Table 4 summarizes the result after first iteration:

Table 4. Pixel Intensity New Value After First Iteration

Pixel $u(x,y)$	1	2	3	4
1	200	200	197,5	197,5
2	200	186,25	197,5	197,5
3	271.25	271.25	293.75	293.75
4	271.25	271.25	293.75	293.75

This process can be repeated over several iterations to stabilize the pixel values and obtain a clearer segmentation between the background and the objects (butterflies). Each iteration allows to reduce the disparity of the intensities while maintaining the key contours of the objects, in our case, the butterflies. The diffusion model with an adjustment for imbalanced data ensures a better consideration of minority classes. The Figure 2 below shows the final result that we will have after many iterations until we have good image segmentation simulated in Python.

Figure 2. Butterfly Image after: a) Binarization, b) Segmentation

DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION

On pixel $u(1, 1)$ the Laplacian is negative because the surrounding pixels have similar values to its value, and therefore there are no large gaps to smooth. The intensity will not change much for this pixel.

We also notice a large gap at the pixel level of $u(3, 1)$ (butterfly = 50, background = 205). The Laplacian is high for this which is a butterfly pixel with a very different intensity from the neighboring pixels. This large gap indicates a strong boundary between the object and the background, which will cause an increase in the intensity to soften this boundary. The action of the external force for $u(3, 1)$ is therefore strong, inducing a significant increase in the intensity of this pixel to compensate for the imbalance in the data. This helps to bring the intensities of the butterflies closer to the background values. The intensity of this pixel increases considerably at the first iteration, due to the high value of the external force applied to the butterfly (minority class). This helps to compensate for the imbalances between the classes.

Then, the diffusion term helps to smooth the transitions between objects and the background, thus we observe a smoothing of the boundaries. In addition, through the adjustment of the external force, the pixels representing the objects that are the butterflies (minority class) are not absorbed by the background. This allows a better segmentation of the objects even in the presence of a strong imbalance between the classes. The pixels representing the background (the first two lines of Table 1) have a small change, because their intensities were already close to the average intensity of the background. In addition, the pixels belonging to the butterflies (the last two lines) have seen their intensities increase considerably, thus compensating for the initial gap with the background. Finally, after the first iteration, we observe a regularization of the pixel intensities. These calculations can be iterated until a stable convergence is obtained in the segmentation of objects (butterflies) and the background.

CONCLUSION

Using the Kolmogorov forward equation with an adapted handling of unbalanced data allows to optimize the segmentation of a binary image. By increasing the external force applied to the minority classes, we manage to preserve the objects while regularizing the boundaries between the objects and the background. This allows a more balanced segmentation and a better differentiation of objects in unbalanced binary images, therefore a progressive regularization. The pixels of the butterflies belonging to the minority class undergo a greater adjustment than those of the background, due to the higher weighting in the external force.

There are several promising avenues of research and technological development to improve the modeling of the segmentation of an image based on artificial intelligence. One of the limitations of approaches based on graphs and external forces is their algorithmic complexity, especially for large images or real-time applications. Future work should aim to improve the computational efficiency of these algorithms and therefore explore parallel and distributed algorithms, particularly by exploiting GPU and cloud computing architectures, to accelerate segmentation processes.

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